

WHITE TONGUE OR FORMATION OF WHITE EYES - CAUSES, METHODS OF TREATMENT

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Abstract. Many people have probably noticed the presence of a white coating on the tongue early in the morning. To eliminate it, the back of some toothbrushes is equipped with special plates. This treatment does not cause any discomfort, is odorless and can be easily removed. But if it thickens, has a creamy consistency and has an unpleasant smell, it can be a symptom of many diseases, including diseases of the gastrointestinal tract.

Keywords: the state of the tongue is a reflection of the state of the gastrointestinal tract, Causes of whiteness of the tongue, Loss of whiteness on the tongue

БЕЛЫЙ ЯЗЫК ИЛИ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ БЕЛЫХ ГЛАЗ – ПРИЧИНЫ, МЕТОДЫ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ

Аннотация. Многие, наверное, замечали наличие белого налета на языке рано утром. Для его устранения тыльная сторона некоторых зубных щеток оснащена специальными пластинами. Эта процедура не вызывает дискомфорта, не имеет запаха и легко удаляется. Но если он густеет, имеет кремообразную консистенцию и имеет неприятный запах, то это может быть симптомом многих заболеваний, в том числе заболеваний желудочно-кишечного тракта.

Ключевые слова: состояние языка отражение состояния желудочно-кишечного тракта, Причины белизны языка, Потеря белизны на языке

THE STATE OF THE TONGUE IS THE OPPOSITE OF THE STATE OF THE GASTROINTESTINAL TRACT

The tongue, or rather its appearance, can give the specialist information about how the gastrointestinal tract is functioning. If a person is healthy, the tongue will have a pale pink color and a smooth, evenly painted surface.

Everyone is familiar with the fact that doctors ask to show the tongue during a medical examination. In this case, the doctor pays attention to the size of the tongue and checks the presence of swelling and tooth marks on its surface.

Thus, the doctor can detect inflammation of the mucous membrane of the gums (gingivitis, stomatitis, myxedema) and acromegaly - hormonal imbalance. Dryness of the surface of the tongue can also occur as a result of acute infectious diseases: flu, diarrhoea, or sepsis. It can also cause incessant vomiting, diarrhea, peritonitis or polyuria.

The condition of the superficial papillary layer and the color of the tongue also serve as a symptom of internal diseases, in which the following diseases are suspected:

Anemia;

Dysfunction of the digestive system;

Hepatitis;

Liver cirrhosis;

Chronic colitis;

Gastritis.

But doctors pay special attention to the whiteness of the tongue - its entire surface or certain parts are covered with a white or slightly yellowish, dense coating - which indicates many possible diseases in the gastrointestinal tract.

CAUSES OF WHITE TONGUE

When healthy people wake up in the morning, the formation of a white coating on the tongue is the result of the accumulation of dead epithelium and temporarily inactive bacteria and their vital activity. When awake, they are constantly washed with saliva.

These beneficial and pathogenic bacteria are present in every organism and they participate in many processes.

This type of tongue caries should be cleaned with circular movements, trying not to damage the tissues. However, there are other, more serious reasons for the formation of catarracts.

An increase in its thickness or a slightly gray color indicates a decrease in immunity, in which case the number of pathogenic bacteria increases.

If the gaze is concentrated on the tip of the tongue or only on the edges, it is necessary to pay attention to the activity of the respiratory system. Sometimes this condition is also observed in smokers.

If white spots appear at the root of the tongue or on the sides of its base, this may indicate developing kidney diseases.

Fungal diseases, in particular, candidiasis or thrush, are manifested by the appearance of curds. In case of angina, the entire surface of the tongue is white, fever is observed, tonsils are enlarged, and difficulty in swallowing is felt.

If teeth marks are detected in the morning, this may be a sign of poor digestion of food in the intestines.

If dense white mucus accumulates in the middle of the tongue and cracks are detected, there is a risk of gastritis.

In some cases, a person can independently make changes to his diet and solve the problem, but it is better to consult a gastroenterologist and follow his recommendations.

LOSS OF THE WHITE LOOK ON THE TONGUE

In the morning, the smell-free look can be simply cleaned with a special brush. However, it cannot be denied that his condition has changed, which is the consequence of health disorders. In this case, it is necessary to eliminate its primary cause.

In the case of white tongue, the first doctor to consult is a therapist. He will give you the right referral after proper checks.

If the problem is detected in time, especially in babies and children, it will be much easier to treat it.

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